

Thought Experiment on General Relativity

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We will discuss about the space time fabric which is the fundamental concept of general relativity and test whether it is correct or not. This discussion is concerned with philosophical aspect of space-time fabric. This discussion is concerned with concept of curvature of space time fabric. We will check the validity of the concept of space-time curvature.

Suppose we take a sponge block and put a heavy spherical ball on it. The heavy ball will create a cavity in the sponge in the region immediately below it. The surface area of sponge near the heavy ball warps or is deformed. This warping of surface remains till we keep the ball on the sponge. When we remove the heavy ball from the sponge, the cavity created by ball will vanish. The upper warped surface will become flat. This phenomenon can be visually observed.

In general relativity, the warping of space time fabric cannot be visually observed. But the warping of space time fabric may be tested by conducting sufficient number of experiments by researchers. These experiments should record large number of different observation and should not use any kind of bias.

In the case of sponge the intermolecular forces between molecules maintains the flatness of the upper surface of sponge. The heavy ball placed on this surface temporarily creates the cavity. But after the removal of the ball, the surface becomes flat .It regains its original shape. The theory of general relativity is many times explained by using the tightened fabric. The same argument can be used for space-time fabric instead of sponge. In general relativity large heavy bodies warp the space-time fabric around them. The magnitude of curvature or the amount of warping of space time fabric is dependent on mass of the bodies. Then by analogy, some questions arise in the mind,

1. Which force or physical entity removes the cavity or warping of space-time fabric after the removal of large heavy bodies?
2. How the space-time fabric maintains its flatness?
3. What is the cause-effect phenomenon responsible for maintaining the flatness of space-time fabric?

Einstein had never answered about these questions. Also these questions are not answered by theory of general relativity. Hence the cause effect principle is not obeyed by the theory of general relativity which is against the basic principle of general relativity. Theory of general relativity was developed by Einstein considering basically the cause effect principle as the bed rock foundation. Curvature of space-time was considered as the main cause of gravity. The basic philosophy of cause-effect is violated by Einstein.

In case of fabric, we can ask the question, how the tightness of fabric is maintained? Generally in the demos of general relativity, the fabric is held tightly at the rim of the container by an external force. The fabric is pulled by the forces at the rim. Then only we can show the demos of concept of general relativity. Then again we can ask the question, what force holds the fabric of space –time at its outermost edges located at infinite distances? The fabric which is not tightly held by any force at rim will not support the weight of any object. This object will fall down.

As far as space is concerned, space is an empty region. Also time is non tangible entity. We can experience its existence but we can't see by our naked eyes. Then question arises in mind, how can a tangible entity like space interact with non tangible entity like time and form structure like space –time fabric? This question is very important and as serious as the question related to action at a distance. Also in quantum mechanics, there are no evidences which support the existence of space time fabric.

In science any concept or theory must be valid at any scales ranging from macroscopic world to microscopic world. General relativity is not applicable at macroscopic world i.e. at galactic level. The problem of galaxy rotation curve cannot be solved by using general theory of relativity. Observed universe should be flat according to general relativity. In reality, the universe is not flat but is expanded in all three dimensions at infinite scale consisting of billions of galaxies. Also the theory of general relativity is not applicable to quantum mechanics. For many years scientist are trying to develop the theory of quantum gravity by combining the theory of general relativity and quantum mechanics. But they have not succeeded until now. In my opinion there is no chance of successfully combining these two, because by very nature these two things are different and contradicting to each other. On one side, General relativity is conceptual thing not proven completely. Whereas on another side, the quantum mechanics deals with laws of nature at microscopic level which is real and completely proven. Obviously the combination of hypothetical unreal entity with real entity is not possible. Also such combination appears to be unnatural.